

Developing Video Copywriting for Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang as a Tourism Destination

Ananda Salsabilah, M. Nadjmuddin*, Sunani, Zidni Ma'ruf, Siti Rahayu, Rizky Aliansyah

Politeknik Negeri Sriwijaya

*Email address: m.nadjmuddin@polsri.ac.id

Received: Nov 11, 2025 | Reviewed: Nov 18, 2025 | Revised: Nov 26, 2025 | Accepted: Dec 6, 2025

ABSTRACT: This study examined the development of a promotional video script for Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang, a traditional boat tour that showcased the cultural heritage of the Musi River. The primary objective was to produce a persuasive, narrative-driven script aimed at attracting both domestic and international tourists. The study adopted the Research and Development (R&D) method proposed by Sukmadinata (2017), which involved three main stages: preliminary study, product development, and final testing. The unit of analysis was a bilingual video script written in both English and Indonesian, structured according to the AIDA model (Attention, Interest, Desire, Action). Data were gathered through observation, interviews, and documentation. The analysis was carried out using a qualitative descriptive approach, drawing on insights from expert evaluations. The findings indicated that it is necessary to integrate cultural storytelling, visual support, and persuasive narrative element. Expert feedback validated the script's clarity and linguistic accuracy. The final product served as a replicable framework for promoting local tourism via digital platforms such as YouTube and TikTok. It was recommended that future promotional efforts continue to involve local community perspectives and uphold cultural authenticity to further strengthen tourism visibility.

Keywords: *Tourism, Video Copywriting, Musi River, Digital Marketing, Narrative Script*

INTRODUCTION

As the capital of South Sumatra, Palembang possesses rich tourism potential stemming from its cultural heritage, historical landmarks, and the legacy of the Sriwijaya Kingdom (Ayudiani, 2022; Faragusta et al., 2025). Tourism in the region is a promising economic alternative that can attract both domestic and international visitors. To effectively capitalize on this potential, innovative and persuasive promotional efforts are necessary, particularly through digital platforms. One specific attraction is Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang, which features traditional Palembang boats—locally known as "ketek"—that serve as a symbol of cultural identity and offer tourists an experience of exploring the Musi River and landmarks like the Ampera Bridge (Oktavia and Heldayani, 2018).

Despite this cultural wealth, many local tourism experiences remain under-promoted in digital formats. In today's digital age, video content has become central to tourism marketing,

with its visual and emotional power strongly influencing travelers' decision-making (Dias and Laveredas, 2024). The key challenge lies in crafting compelling narratives that effectively communicate the uniqueness and appeal of these attractions. This necessitates the use of effective video copywriting, which includes the textual and narrative elements like scripting, captions, and voiceovers. Effective copywriting must blend engaging storytelling with strategic messaging to deliver both emotional impact and clear information (Hudson and Thal, 2023).

Current promotional efforts for the *ketek* tour are often limited to static images or descriptive text, lacking the structured, emotionally resonant narratives that modern digital audiences demand. As Palembang aims for greater visibility in national and international tourism, there is a clear and immediate need for high-quality promotional videos supported by strategic copywriting. The focus of this final report is to address this gap by developing persuasive video copywriting to promote Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang as a key tourism attraction.

The central question guiding this research is: How can video copywriting be developed for *Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang* as a tourist attraction? This study aims to develop a clear, compelling, and effective video copywriting strategy specifically for this destination. To achieve this, the research scope focuses on two main areas: first, the development of structured and persuasive video copywriting that highlights the cultural and historical significance of the tour boat; and second, the creation of high-quality digital promotional content that aligns with modern audience expectations for platforms like YouTube and TikTok. This product, designed with optimal digital formats and bilingual considerations (Indonesian with English subtitles), will serve as a replicable model for other culturally grounded tourism videos, offering practical benefits to local stakeholders and expanding the theoretical understanding of persuasive practice within tourism discourse.

METHOD

This research employed a Research and Development (R&D) methodology, specifically following the three main phases proposed by Sukmadinata (2017): the Preliminary Study, Model Development, and Final Product Testing. The primary goal was to develop and validate a persuasive video copywriting script for *Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang*.

The data was gained through three primary techniques: observation, interviews, and documentation. An interview was conducted directly with Mr. Alfarish, the owner of *Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang*, to gather detailed information on the attraction's history, features, and operational procedures. Observation was conducted through direct field visits to the Pasar 16 Ilir dock to document the environment, facilities, and services offered, which led to the initial Model Draft of the script.

The Model Development stage involved two steps of iterative testing. Limited Testing involved presenting the initial script to experts for validation: Mr. Ahmad Iman (Content Flow and Bahasa Indonesia expert) and Mr. Welly Ardiansyah (English Linguistics expert). The script was then revised based on their feedback. The Wider Testing involved presenting the refined script to the target audience, including the business owner and his staff, to ensure the final product aligned with user expectations. The final draft was achieved after incorporating feedback from both experts and users, completing the product development stage as recommended for final report researchers.

RESULT

The initial stage of this research was the Preliminary Study, which encompassed a literature review, a field survey, and the creation of the initial model draft. The literature review focused on the AIDA model (Attention, Interest, Desire, Action) and narrative copywriting styles (Sofyan et al., 2023), supported by Mayer's (2005) Cognitive Theory of Multimedia Learning, to

establish the theoretical basis for the video script structure. The Field Survey involved direct observation, documentation, and interviews at *Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang*, collecting essential details about services, routes, and the founder's backstory to ensure an authentic and fact-based narrative. This data resulted in the Model Draft, a bilingual promotional video script structured according to the AIDA model, designed for adaptability across digital platforms like YouTube and TikTok.

The initial script draft underwent Limited Testing involving three experts for validation and refinement:

Content Flow and Bahasa Indonesia Expert (Mr. Ahmad Iman Mulyadi): Recommended restructuring the script's hook (Attention) to be more engaging and improving transitions to enhance the cultural tone and narrative depth.

English Linguistics Expert (Mr. Welly Ardiansyah): Corrected vocabulary, refined sentence structure, and ensured professionalism by replacing contractions with full forms (e.g., *It's* to *It is*) for clarity in the English version.

Copywriting Expert (Ms. Aisyah Shahab): Suggested strengthening the closing (Call to Action/CTA) with a more memorable and branded tagline: "*Ketek Wisata @3, where every ripple tells a story.*"

Following expert revision, the script proceeded to Wider Testing with the target audience, including the business owner and customers. This feedback led to a final refinement in the CTA section, with the addition of a more urgent call to action: "*Do not wait any longer, book now and immerse yourself in the story-filled atmosphere of the Musi River with Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang.*" The script was then finalized, serving as the Final Product for this development stage.

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

The research utilized the AIDA model (Attention, Interest, Desire, Action) as the core structural framework for developing the *video copywriting* for *Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang*. This choice proved highly effective as the AIDA model provides a logical, coherent, and psychologically sound narrative flow essential for marketing purposes.

The initial Attention section was rigorously tested and refined to ensure it immediately captured the audience in the fast-paced digital content environment. Expert revision transformed the initial, somewhat passive query into an emotionally resonant statement that speaks directly to the audience's need for a different, more fulfilling holiday experience ("*Have you ever felt tired of the same old holiday choices?*").

The subsequent Interest and Desire sections were crucial for building emotional engagement and communicating the product's Unique Selling Proposition (USP). By including the narrative backstory of the founder, Mr. Alfarish, and the familial symbolism of the "@3" in the name, the script successfully established a heart and personal dimension to the brand.

This strategic use of storytelling transformed the traditional boat into an experience with emotional depth, aligning with principles of narrative *copywriting* that emphasize connection over pure facts. The adoption of a narrative style in the script was a direct implementation of persuasive communication theory, which holds that effective messages must appeal to the audience's emotions and values. In the context of Palembang tourism, the script aimed to sell not just a boat ride, but a *healing* and nostalgic experience ("*enjoy the calm flow of the Musi River*").

The feedback from the Indonesian Language expert was vital in this aspect, ensuring the narrative's cultural tone and depth were enhanced. Their suggestion to pivot the narrative away from generic vacation comparisons (malls or cafés) and focus specifically on the unique experience of the Musi River underscored the product's differentiation.

This focus on localized creativity and originality supports the idea that promotional content must stand out to trigger positive emotional responses (Dias and Laveredas, 2024), which is a prerequisite for favorable destination perception.

The multi-tiered validation process (Limited and Wider Testing) was indispensable in ensuring the final product's quality and functionality. Feedback from the Linguistics expert guaranteed that the English script met professional and academic standards, which is necessary for targeting international audiences. Attention to detail, such as replacing contractions, enhances the perception of the content's professionalism.

The Copywriting expert's contribution, particularly the introduction of the branded tagline ("*Ketek Wisata @3, where every ripple tells a story.*"), provided a powerful and memorable closing identity. This tagline effectively repositions *Ketek Wisata @3* as a repository of stories and memories, rather than just a travel service.

Finally, the Wider Testing with the target audience provided crucial functional verification. The suggestion to include a more urgent Call to Action ("*Do not wait any longer, book now...*") was critical in maximizing the script's persuasive potential, ensuring that the built-up interest is converted into a concrete booking action, thereby completing the AIDA cycle effectively.

Although the research successfully completed the Model Development and validation stages, it was constrained by the strict academic timeline typical of a diploma project. This limitation prevented the research from progressing to a comprehensive *Final Product Testing* and dissemination phase. Consequently, key metrics of long-term success, such as the script's actual impact on audience engagement, conversion rates, and revenue generation, could not be assessed.

The study is therefore limited to the development and internal validation of the promotional material, providing a rigorously refined final script that is ready for implementation.

This research offers a theoretical contribution to understanding persuasive copywriting in tourism and a practical, actionable model for local tourism stakeholders to enhance the visibility and appeal of *Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang*.

CONCLUSIONS

The writer concludes that the video copywriting developed for "Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang" serves as a promotional tool for this traditional boat tour along the Musi River, aiming to highlight its cultural heritage and attract both domestic and international tourists. This bilingual video script, available in both English and Indonesian, is structured effectively using the AIDA model (Attention, Interest, Desire, Action) and was intended for videos lasting three to four minutes, suitable for platforms such as YouTube and TikTok.

The script comprised four key components. The Attention section-initiated viewer engagement by introducing the idea of meaningful journeys through simplicity, nostalgia, and emotional storytelling. The Interest and Desire sections provided informative content about the background, development, uniqueness, and main features of *Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang*. The script concluded with a persuasive Call to Action, inviting viewers to experience the tour in person while also offering practical information on booking and promotions. The script development followed a Research and Development (R&D) methodology as proposed by Sukmadinata (2017), which involved a preliminary study, product development, and validation through both limited testing with experts in content flow and language, and wider testing with the owner and staff of *Ketek Wisata @3 Palembang*. Feedback from these experts confirmed the script's clarity and linguistic accuracy, and the results showed that the integration of cultural narratives, visual elements, and persuasive storytelling significantly improved its promotional effectiveness.

Due to financial limitations and the complexity of the production process, the writer focused on refining the script into its final draft based on expert and user feedback, without

advancing to the final product testing or distribution.

REFERENCES

- Albrighton, T. (2013). *The abc of copywriting*. Norwich: ABC Business Communications Ltd.
- Awware. (2021). What is AIDA model: steps, approaches and examples. Awware. Diakses Juli 10, 2025, dari <https://awware.co/blog/aida-model/>
- Ayudiani, A. (2022). Musi River tourism area planning and development as a tourist attraction to increase the number of tourist visits to Palembang City. *The 2nd International Hospitality Entrepreneurship & Innovation Conference 2022*, 1(1), 124.
- Budimansyah, D., Fitriyani, S., Iswandi, D., Muthaqqin, D. I., & Yudistira, R. (2019). AIDA model PC extension (Attention, Interest, Desire, Action, Based Projectcitizen) to address the practice of bullying among students in the regency of Pangandaran. In *5th UPI International Conference on Technical and Vocational Education and Training (ICTVET 2018)* (pp. 527-534). Atlantis Press.
- Creswell, J. W. (2017). *Research design: Qualitative, quantitative, and mixed methods approaches*. Sage publications.
- Dias, F., & Lavaredas, A. M. (2024). Assessing the Effectiveness of Tourism Promotional Videos: Creativity, Emotional Impact, Perceived Quality, and Attitude Towards the Destination. *Administrative Sciences*, 14(12), 323.
- Faragusta, A. L., Wasitoh, M., & Purwanto, M. B. (1924). Writing a video script to promote Balaputra Dewa Museum as a cultural tourism attraction in Palembang. *PUSTAKA: Jurnal Bahasa Dan Pendidikan*, 5 (2 SE-Articles), 12–23.
- Fauziah, P. W., & Hendrayati, H. (n.d) Tourism Attractions on Visiting Decisions: A Literature Review. *Tourism and Hospitality Essentials Journal*, 14(2), 1-10.
- Gall, M. D., Gall, P. J., & Borg, W. R. (2007). *Educational research: An introduction*. Pearson Education.
- Guarda, T., Augusto, M. F., Victor, J. A., Mazón, L. M., Lopes, I., & Oliveira, P. (2021). The impact of TikTok on digital marketing. In *Marketing and Smart Technologies: Proceedings of ICMarTech 2020* (pp. 35-44). Singapore: Springer Singapore.
- Halim, N. W. A., Amin, H., & Susilawaty, F. T. (2024). Strategi copywriting@ beauty Kendari: Pendekatan teori AIDA dalam meningkatkan engagement konsumen. *Jurnal Ilmu Komunikasi UHO: Jurnal Penelitian Kajian Ilmu Komunikasi dan Informasi*, 9(1), 239–

249.

- Hernández, E. (2016). The Art of Copywriting: Writing copy for an overstimulated world. In *Leading Creative Teams: Management Career Paths for Designers, Developers, and Copywriters* (pp. 129-139). Berkeley, CA: Apress.
- Hudson, S., & Thal, K. (2013). The impact of social media on the consumer decision process: Implications for tourism marketing. *Journal of Travel & Tourism Marketing*, 30(1-2), 156-160.
- Kawulich, B. B. (2005). Participant observation as a data collection method. In *Forum qualitative sozialforschung/forum: Qualitative social research* (Vol. 6, No. 2).
- Kvale, S., & Brinkmann, S. (2009). *Interviews: Learning the craft of qualitative research interviewing* (2nd ed.). SAGE Publications.
- Lew, A. A. (1987). A framework of tourist attraction research. *Annals of tourism research*, 14(4), 553-575.
- Mayer, R. E. (2005). Cognitive theory of multimedia learning. *The Cambridge handbook of multimedia learning*, 41(1), 31-48.
- Musman, A. (2023). *The Art of Copywriting: Cara Mudah Mendapatkan Konsumen dan Mencetak Cuan di Atas Rata-rata*. Anak Hebat Indonesia.
- Nadjmuddin, M., Nabilla, R., Kurniati, D., Lutfiyatun, E., Akbar, A., & Fadhillah, R. (2023). Developing A Video Copywriting to Promote Palembang Traditional Cakes. *EDUTOURISM Journal Of Tourism Research*, 5(02), 268-283.
- Oktavia, M., & Heldayani, E. (2018). Potency of waterfront tourism in Palembang. In *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* (Vol. 145, No. 1, p. 012072). IOP Publishing.
- Pratama, B., Innayah, M., Furqon, M., & Purwokerto, U. (2023). Improving MSMEs' Networking through Digital Marketing: The Role of Copywriting. *Indonesian Journal of Business Analytics*. <https://doi.org/10.55927/ijba.v3i3.4588>.
- Shahab, A., Hutagalung, G. U., Rohliah, L., Lutfiyatun, E., Pasya, A. F., Rohman, F., & Stefanus, G. C. (2024). Bilingual E-Book: A Platform to Promote Culinary Tourism from Palembang. *EDUTOURISM Journal Of Tourism Research*, 6(02), 92-104.
- Simpson, C. (2016). *The Advertising Solution: Influence Prospects, Multiply Sales, and Promote Your Brand*. Entrepreneur Press.
- Sofyan, A., Yuniati, Y., & Ratnasari, A. (2023). *Copywriting Marketing in Reaching the Target*

- Market. KnE Social Sciences, 466-475.
- Suleman, D. (2023). Strategi Copywriting Untuk Menulis Promosi Offline Atau Online. PaKMas: Jurnal Pengabdian Kepada Masyarakat, 3(1), 1-6.
- Sukmadinata. N.S. (2017). Metode penelitian Pendidikan. Bandung: PT Remaja Rosda Karya.
Retrieved March 13, 2023
- Trijanto, A. (2001). Copywriting: Seni mengasah kreativitas dan memahami bahasa iklan. Bandung: Remaja Rosdakarya.
- Yuniningsih, T., Dwimawanti, I. H., & Lituhayu, D. (2023). Supporting Factors in The Development of Muslim Friendly Tourism in Palembang City. PERSPEKTIF, 12(2), 413-421.